

№3
27.06.2023

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION
TADQIQ VA TATBIQ
ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

CERTIFICATE
№ 078777

INDEX COPERNICUS
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t.f.b. PhD

Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligida
2023-yil 3-mayda
№078777
raqam bilan ro'yxatga
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STUDY OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS IN UZBEKISTAN AT THE LEVEL OF STATE POLICY

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Abstract: Demographic processes occurring all over the world today, rapid use of techniques and technologies in production, growth of transport networks, large-scale construction of large industrial enterprises, have led to huge changes in human life. But at the same time. It also causes a number of problems. It causes the same problems. One such problem is the environmental problem.

Keywords: ecology, atmosphere, biodiversity, nature, conservation, cooperation, law, water resources, natural resources, environment, risk, health, national, local, global, problem.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПРОБЛЕМ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ НА УРОВНЕ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ

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Аннотация: Демографические процессы, происходящие сегодня во всем мире, бурное использование техники и технологий в производстве, рост транспортных сетей, масштабное строительство крупных промышленных предприятий, привели к огромным изменениям в жизни человека. Но в то же время. Это также вызывает ряд проблем. Это вызывает те же проблемы. Одной из таких проблем является экологическая проблема.

Ключевые слова: экология, атмосфера, биоразнообразие, природа, охрана, сотрудничество, право, водные ресурсы, природные ресурсы, окружающая среда, риск, здоровье, национальная, локальная, глобальная, проблема.

Environmental problems have become the most global problems facing humanity today. In particular, the problem of preserving the diversity of the earth's crust, fresh water, atmospheric air, flora and fauna has become one of the most pressing issues facing mankind. As a person lives as an integral part of nature, a favorable climate, clean air, clean water and biological diversity are extremely

necessary for him to live. From this point of view, since the 2nd half of the 20th century, environmental problems have become somewhat urgent. That is why prestigious international organizations have adopted a number of international protocols on the protection of fresh water sources and the protection of nature. In many countries of the world, parties dealing with environmental issues have emerged today. As a result, these parties began to take part in the parliamentary elections. From the first years of independence, Uzbekistan developed its own environmental policy with a serious approach to environmental issues. The main goal of this policy is to preserve the Aral Sea, which is considered one of the global problems in the region, not to harm biodiversity, to use transboundary lessons based on the ecological situation in the region, to ensure the purity of atmospheric air, and to make effective use of world experiences in the processing of household waste. That is why environmental issues have risen to the level of state policy in Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan has also developed its own environmental policy, joining a number of international agreements and protocols on global environmental problems. The basic purpose of this policy embodies vital issues related to the rational solution of local, national and global environmental problems. From this point of view, the leadership of Uzbekistan has its own goals in discussing the issue of the island at a number of prestigious meetings of the UN. Uzbekistan has developed its national environmental policy in order to prevent the environmental crisis by in-depth analysis of the causes and consequences of environmental problems in general. In addition, a branch of the Ecosan international organization, an environmental protection committee and an ecological party are operating in the Republic. The main goal of these prestigious organizations is to stabilize the environmental situation. That is why a number of laws, decrees and state programs on environmental issues have been adopted in Uzbekistan. The article provides comprehensive information about the environmental situation in Uzbekistan, environmental threats that threaten the life of the Republic and their main aspects, as well as environmental policy in the Republic in the years of independence and its goals and results. At present, many environmental problems seriously threaten the sustainable development of human society. Violation of the ecological balance, gradual deterioration of natural structures, damage to the integrity of the biosphere, serious damage to the quality of the environment necessary for the vital activity of the society. Uzbekistan also inherited severe environmental problems from the former Soviet state. In particular, environmental risks related to the drying up of the Aral Sea, salinization of the land, serious pollution of water sources and atmospheric air, the annual increase in the amount of household waste, and the increasing risk of extinction of some species of flora and fauna threaten the life of today's Uzbekistan. It should be noted that the Republic of Uzbekistan has a decisive role in ensuring regional environmental security. Because, with its natural resources, intellectual and economic opportunities, Uzbekistan plays an important role in

solving global and regional problems. In the 80s of the last century, the environmental situation in Uzbekistan started to become serious. In particular, the environmental crisis related to the drying up of the Aral Sea, the problems related to the use of toxic chemicals in agriculture and its consequences required drastic measures to be taken to prevent an ecological crisis in the region and protect the environment. Therefore, in April 1988, the Committee for Nature Protection of Uzbekistan SSR was established. After Uzbekistan gained independence, it became possible to make a correct assessment of the ecological situation in the republic. In addition, the issue of environmental protection and achieving ecological stability has risen to the level of state policy. The environmental threats that threaten Uzbekistan today can be classified as follows.

1. Global problems (climate changes, depletion of the ozone layer, drying up of the Aral Sea, fresh water problem).

2. Regional problems: the negative ecological situation related to the drying up of the Aral Sea, regional problems related to the use of water resources, transboundary pollution of the environment, desertification, the spread of infectious and extremely dangerous diseases, natural and man-made problems).

3. National environmental problems are lack of water resources and pollution, problems of providing the population with clean drinking water, problems of landslides and floods, atmospheric air pollution, preservation of biodiversity, problems related to public health, rational use of natural resources, problems related to industrial and household waste).

4. Local environmental problems (radiation pollution of certain areas, rise and pollution of underground water) can be listed.

Due to the drying up of the Aral Sea, a set of complex socio-economic problems of an international character in origin and consequences has arisen.

That is why the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, assessed the issue as follows. "We are witnessing the disappearance of one of the largest closed water bodies in the world within 20-25 years. However, it has not yet happened that an entire sea perished before the eyes of one generation."

The island crisis is one of the biggest environmental and humanitarian tragedies in human history. About 35 million people living in the sea basin were affected by it.

Therefore, it is not for nothing that the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the 72nd and 75th sessions of the UN, drew the attention of the world community to the situation related to the island problem. Another serious environmental problem in the republic is the problem of soil erosion. Cultivated areas, land resources are constantly damaged by various types of erosion. For example, if we pay attention to the data of 2004, 2,790,000 hectares (339,000 hectares of irrigated land) were damaged due to water erosion in the republic. Active use of biological objects leads to deterioration of living conditions of plants and animals, reduction of their species

and total number. In particular, during the next decade, the number of rare and endangered plant species included in the "Red Book" of the Republic of Uzbekistan increased from 163 to 305 species. It is extremely sad that this situation corresponds to 80 percent of the total plant life in the republic. In addition, 161 species of animals were included in the "Red Book" published in 1981, and in 2004 this figure was 184 species. As a result of subordination of the economy of the republic to the interests of the economy of the Union and the emergence of cotton monopolies during the former Union period, more than 20 types of pesticides were used in the fight against serious pests not only of the republic's economy, but also of nature. Due to the excessive use of these poisons, the amount of toxic substances in the cultivated areas has reached several times higher than the prescribed indicators. Today, there are 13 cemeteries of toxic chemicals in the territory of the Republic, where banned toxic chemicals and mineral fertilizers, as well as containers of expired toxic chemical preparations, are buried, their volume is 9 thousand tons. The environmental problem related to air pollution is also considered one of the most urgent issues. We can see serious air pollution in Angren, Almalyk, Bekobod, Tashkent, Chirchik, Fergana and Navoi, which are industrial cities of the republic. The problem of protecting the environment from pollution from production and consumption is related to the problem of rational and comprehensive use of natural resources and the implementation of cleaner production technologies. The main sources of environmental pollution are the waste generated in energy, non-ferrous and ferrous metallurgy, chemical industry and construction industry facilities. The annual volume of production and consumption waste in the republic is more than 100 million tons, more than 14 percent of which are toxic. Another environmental problem in the republic is the problem of water resources. Uzbekistan is located in a rather unfavorable natural environment in terms of water supply. The uneven location of the transboundary rivers of Central Asia causes a number of inconveniences in the use of water sources. For example, the long-term average river flow in the Syr Darya River basin is 37.9 cubic km per year. At the same time, for many years, on average, in Kyrgyzstan, 28.0 cubic km per year, 73.8%), in Uzbekistan, 5.59 cubic km, 14.8%. The perennial resources of the Amudarya basin are more than 78 cubic km, of which 62.9 km cubic more than 80 percent) is formed on the territory of Tajikistan. In Uzbekistan, only 4.7 cubic km (6 percent) of it is contained. As it is known from the above examples, water sources are quite limited in the Republic, and this situation requires efficient and rational use of water. So, environmental problems are considered an active universal problem that humanity has to face. Especially in the 21st century, this problem is getting serious. This requires humanity to treat nature with care.

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